

THE EFFECT OF THE CARBON/EPOXY INTERFACE ON DAMAGE ACCUMULATION DURING FATIGUE.

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ABSTRACT

To study the influence of the interface properties on damage accumulation, fatigue tests were performed on a carbon/epoxy system in which the carbon fibres had received different levels of surface treatment. For a first group of fatigue tests, the damage threshold obtained in monotonic tensile tests, was chosen as maximum stress level. For a second group, the same maximum stress was chosen for all specimens. In both cases, the R-ratio was 0.1. Damage growth was monitored using different NDT-techniques. From radiography results, it was observed that the cracks which initiate at the specimen edge, immediately span the entire specimen width, except for the untreated material. Important differences in the growth rate of transverse cracks were found. The presence and density of other damage types (angle cracks, delaminations, fibre failure) was also strongly influenced by the carbon fibre surface treatment.

Keywords: carbon fibre, interface, fatigue, damage development, NDT-techniques

1. INTRODUCTION

It is known that the surface treatment of the fibres changes the fibre surface morphology and chemistry [1,2] and can improve the fibre-matrix bond strength. This can be measured with fragmentation tests [3]. On the other hand, a decrease in individual fibre strength caused by the oxidative surface treatment of the fibre, is often found [4]. However, the data reduction in these micromechanical tests is not straightforward and extensive modeling is often needed to obtain accurate results [5]. In addition, most of the micromechanical tests are performed on idealised single fibre composites. Therefore, direct investigation of the macro-mechanical properties is necessary. The bond between a fibre and the surrounding matrix takes care of the stress transfer between fibre and matrix, and will thus influence the mechanical properties of a composite. Because a bad interface contains flaws, it will also influence the initiation and growth of different damage modes like matrix cracking and delaminations. The last few years, some work has been done concerning macromechanical properties and damage development [6,7,8,9,10], showing that not all the properties are positively influenced by the fibre surface treatment. However, none of the mentioned work has focused on the fatigue behaviour of composites. In this paper, attention is paid on the effect of the carbon fibre surface treatment on damage development during tension-tension fatigue loading of cross-plyed $(0_2,90_2)_S$ laminates.

2. MATERIAL AND TEST TECHNIQUES

2.1. Material

Intermediate modulus carbon fibres IM 43-750 (tensile strength: 5.5 GPa, E-modulus: 300 GPa), made by Courtaulds Ltd. were used for this study. The carbon fibres received four levels of a wet oxidative surface treatment:

- 0% SST (SST = Standard Surface Treatment): untreated fibres
- 10% SST: fibres which received 10% of the normal commercial surface treatment
- 50% SST: fibres which received half of the normal surface treatment.
- 100% SST: commercially treated fibres

All fibres were sized 1 % by weight (size designated size "A").

A toughened epoxy system, HG 9106 by Courtaulds Ltd. was chosen as matrix material. The epoxy system is a blend of di-, tri- and tetrafunctional epoxies with 3.3 DDS hardener. The ductility and thus fracture toughness is improved by adding thermoplastic poly-ethersulphone. The following properties of the pure matrix are given: tensile strength: 40 MPa; E-modulus: 3.1 GPa; elongation at break: 3.5 %; matrix fracture toughness $G_{IC,m}$: 200 J/m².

Cross-ply (0₂,90₂)_S plates were laminated by hand lay-up. The laminates were produced at both laboratories following the standard cure cycle, recommended by Courtaulds Ltd.: 3.5 hours at 120°C and 3.5 hours at 177°C, at a constant pressure of 700 kPa. After production, the quality of the plates was inspected with the ultrasonic C-scanning technique. Specimens were cut by a water cooled diamond cutting wheel (dimensions 250 x 20 x 1 mm). The specimen edges were polished. Aluminium end-tabs were mounted onto the specimen ends. The specimens were subsequently kept in a dessicator at room temperature until testing. All tests were performed at room temperature in normal environmental conditions.

2.2. Damage monitoring techniques

In order to obtain a better understanding of the initiation and growth of the damage modes, and the interaction between them, different non-destructive test techniques are used to measure the amount of damage. The techniques used in the present work are: acoustic emission, microscopy (or edge replication technique), ultrasonic C-scanning and penetrant enhanced radiography. Table 1 presents the potential of the different techniques. The deply technique is added to the table, although it is a destructive technique: it is based on the pyrolysis of the matrix material. From table 1 it is clear that the acoustic emission (AE) technique is the only technique which can possibly detect all different damage modes. Also, the AE technique continuously monitors the damage. For all other techniques, the test has to be stopped temporarily. However, the distinction between the acoustic emission signals coming from different damage modes is not straightforward. The damage detection techniques mentioned in table 1 and used to document the damage introduced due to mechanical loading are described briefly.

2.2.1. Optical damage monitoring techniques

For many polymer composites, it is possible to use the edge replica technique to monitor the damage at the polished specimen edge. However, since some acetone is used in this technique, it cannot be used for some epoxy matrices. For the HG9106-epoxy system it was found that the acetone created cracks. Therefore, light microscopy directly on the specimen edge (magn. 300x) was used to scan the surface over a length of 20 mm.

2.2.2. Acoustic emission

High frequency sound waves which are created by a phase transformation, cracking and plastic

Table 1: Overview of the different damage detection techniques which can be used to monitor the different damage types.

	acoustic emission	ultrasonic c-scan	penetrant radiography	microscopy	deply*
fibre fracture	possible	no	no	no**	yes
delamination	possible	yes	yes	at the edge	yes
matrix cracking	possible	no	yes	at the edge	-
debonding	possible	no	no	no	-

* The deply technique is a destructive technique, but shows important data on fibre failure and was therefore included in this table. The delamination detection depends upon the use of AuCl₂, which is deposited on free surfaces.

** Fibre fracture cannot be measured using microscopy. It is however possible to detect fibre failure at the specimen edge by using the edge replication technique. The replica can be used in a scanning electron microscope to visualise the damage.

deformation, can be detected using the acoustic emission (AE) technique. The AE signal is not often recorded as a whole (because it consumes too much computer memory), but is mostly described, after computer analysis, by some characteristics, as shown in figure 1. During the propagation of the elastic wave through the material, the real characteristics of the signal at the source are altered. Nevertheless, some characteristics of the AE source are still dominantly present when the AE signal is captured by the sensor [11].

The results were obtained using an AET 5500B system (Acoustic Emission Technology Co.) At all times, two transducers are mounted on the specimen leaving a distance of about 50 mm between them. Both resonant and wide band sensors are used. A couplant, type SC6, is used to obtain a good signal transfer between specimen and sensor. Precautions were taken to eliminate mechanical and electronic noise, created during the test. The length over which the AE-signals were analysed was about 45 mm.

2.2.3. Ultrasonic C-scanning

Whereas the above described techniques are used while the specimen is mounted in the fatigue testing machine, the specimens have to be unmounted and submerged in a water tank for the ultrasonic C-scanning. Therefore, the measurements were performed after $5 \cdot 10^4$ and 10^5 cycles only. The specimens were scanned over a surface of 40 by 20 mm with a step size of 0.1 mm. The focal spot of the beam was 0.12 mm. A high frequency (50 MHz) emitter-receiver was used to enable distinction between the different layers in the composite specimen. In this way delaminations at the 0-90-interfaces could be visualised. Transverse matrix cracks cannot be observed, unless a small delamination has been created at the transverse crack. After C-scanning, the specimens were dried at 100°C for one hour. Influence of the submersion on further damage development was not observed.

2.2.4. Penetrant enhanced radiography

Due to the small difference in the mass absorption coefficients of the composite and the air (filling cracks and delaminations), it is necessary to fill the cracks with a radio opaque liquid penetrant. A Zinc Iodide solution and Diiodomethane are used [12]. However, a strong stress corrosive effect of the penetrant on the matrix system used in this study, was observed. Therefore, the specimens were submerged in the penetrant at the end of the test (10^6 cycles) only.

2.3. Fatigue test parameters.

All tests were performed with an R-ratio ($\sigma_{min}/\sigma_{max}$) of 0.1. A test frequency of 1 Hz was chosen to allow accurate data acquisition with the AE-equipment. Two different maximum stress levels were chosen. In the first series of tests, the maximum stress level was equal to the threshold stress for transverse crack initiation (i.e. the stress at which the first transverse crack occurs), observed during

Figure 1: Transverse crack growth as a function of the applied strain during monotonic tensile loading.

monotonic tensile loading. As can be seen in figure 1, the specimens containing untreated fibres already have some cracks due to the thermal stresses, present in the material after curing. The crack density remains constant up to 0.3 % of mechanical strain, which might indicate that the thermal stresses have been released by cutting the specimens. For the fatigue work, the stress corresponding to a strain of 0.3 %, i.e. 296 MPa was chosen. The other stress levels were 456, 624 and 711 MPa for the 10, 50 and 100 % SST specimens respectively. For the second series of tests, the same maximum stress level of 624 MPa was chosen for all specimens.

3. TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the fatigue tests, different types of damage could be distinguished. Each type is schematically shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Schematic view of the damage at the edge of the specimens. The different damage types, as they are presented in the following figures are shown.

3.1. σ_{max} = damage threshold stress

Figure 3 presents the results of the first test series (with the damage threshold stress as maximum stress level). As can be seen from figure 3a, the untreated specimens show a very high 90° crack density after 1 cycle, which is slightly higher than the crack density at 0.3 % strain in figure 1. During the following fatigue cycles, the density remains constant. This is mainly caused by the very low maximum stress level. Simultaneously however, a strong increase of angle cracks is found. Angle cracks are created by shear stresses in the 90° layer, which are present due to the load reintroduction. Because of the low shear strength of the composite, the shear stress quickly exceeds the shear strength, thus creating the angle cracks. Their presence increases the length over which the load is reintroduced greatly. This means that the regions in the 90° ply where the nominal stress is reached, become shorter. It is therefore doubtful that the same transverse crack density as during monotonic testing will be reached.

It is often found that a 90° crack immediately spans the entire thickness of the ply. However, in the 0 % SST and (to a much less extent) in the 10 % SST specimens, short 90° cracks (cf. fig. 2) are present. This is only possible if the local 90°-strength varies greatly. The crack initiates at a weak spot (a large flaw), but is stopped, because the surrounding material is much stronger. In some cases, the short cracks grow over the entire thickness during further loading, but the total number of short cracks is almost constant throughout the test, which is surprising.

The 10 % and 50 % SST specimens show very similar behaviour. The increase of transverse cracks is gradual, and even after 100000 cycles, a saturation level is not reached. After 500 cycles, a change of the slope in the crack density curve is found. This means that, during the first cycles, small defects are gradually growing in size until a critical flaw size is reached, and the cracks grow in an unstable way. A sharp increase of both angle cracks and edge delaminations is found after about 2000 cycles for both 10 and 50 % SST specimen. This is an important difference, compared with the untreated specimens, where only angle cracks are present. A delamination will initiate if the strain energy release rate G_{del} exceeds the critical fracture toughness G_c of the 0-90 interface. An angle crack will grow if the strain energy release rate G_{45} in the 90° layer exceeds the fracture toughness of the 90° layer. The energy release rates are influenced by the stress condition, not by the fibre surface treatment. Therefore, the ratio G_{del}/G_{45} is constant. The 0-90 interface consists of a matrix rich layer, and is therefore governed by the matrix properties. Therefore, it can be stated that the fracture toughness of the 0-90 interface is almost constant as the fibre-matrix interface properties are changed. However, the fracture toughness of the 90° layer is strongly influenced by the fibre surface treatment, as was repor-

Figure 3: Damage development during fatigue with the damage threshold as maximum stress level. a: 0 % SST; b: 10 % SST; c: 50 % SST; d: 100 % SST.

ted by some of the authors [9]. For the untreated fibres, the G_c of the 90° layer is low, and angle cracks will develop preferentially. For the 10 and 50 % SST however, the G_c of the 90° layer has doubled, which makes the initiation of angle cracks more difficult. Therefore also delaminations are present. This corresponds with the results of the authors in [9]: it was shown that the G_{IC} and G_{IIC} of the composites containing 10 and 50 % SST fibres are almost the same as the matrix fracture toughness.

In the standard treated specimens, the crack density is the lowest, although the maximum stress level is very high. The postponed creation of transverse cracks shows that the defect size is small, compared to the other materials. As can be seen from figure 3d, the amount of delaminations is higher than the amount of angle cracks. This is also in correspondence with [9], where the 100 % SST composite fracture toughness was found to be twice the matrix fracture toughness. However, it has to be pointed out that, if structural integrity is concerned, delaminations are a more severe damage type.

3.2. $\sigma_{max} = \text{constant value}$

In figure 4, the damage development is shown of the specimens tested at the same maximum stress level. The same conclusions as presented above, can be repeated. It seems that the transverse crack

Figure 4: : Damage development during fatigue (maximum stress level: 624 MPa).
a: 0 % SST; b: 10 % SST; c: 50 % SST; d: 100 % SST.

density decreases with increasing surface treatment. This is remarkable, because of the important difference in density of the other damage types: a high amount of angle cracks or delaminations renders the load reintroduction into the 90° layer more difficult. Therefore, a larger distance between the transverse cracks could be expected in the material with low treatment fibres.

In the 0 % SST specimens, ply splitting is present. The distinction with a delamination is rather arbitrary: ply splitting is in fact a delamination growing between two 90° layers. The presence of these delaminations again shows the high flaw density and the very poor quality of the untreated material. No ply splitting was observed in other specimens. Comparing figures 4b, c and d shows that the delamination density is still the lowest in the standard treated material.

Overall, it can be stated that the crack density decreases strongly with increased fibre surface treatment. Already with a low degree of surface treatment, important improvements are found.

It has to be pointed out that it is very risky to draw conclusions based on delaminations, observed by light microscopy. First of all, the delaminations are not opened, and their detection is therefore not easy. Secondly, slight misorientation of the fibres, leads to cutting of some 0° fibres at the edges. At these places, delaminations can easily occur. This can be seen from figure 4c, where a very high delamination density was observed. This was not repeated in the C-scanning results, where the delamination density was of the same order as the 10 % SST material.

Comparing the damage density after 10⁵ cycles with the radiography results, no significant difference

Figure 5: Distribution graphs of the peak amplitude of the AE signals generated during fatigue (after 50000 cycles) of $(0_2, 90_2)_S$ laminates (maximum stress: 624 MPa, $R = 0.1$) a: distribution for a 0 % SST specimen; b: distribution for a 50 % SST specimen; c: distribution for a 100 % SST.

was found between the 90° cracks and the number of cracks spanning the entire specimen width. This shows that a crack, spanning the entire 90° thickness immediately grows over the entire 90° ply (unlike many other carbon/epoxies [13,14,15]). Nevertheless, some small cracks at the specimen edges could be observed in the X-ray photographs (especially in the untreated specimens). These are likely to be the angle cracks, observed in light microscopy.

In figure 5, the distribution curves of the Peak Amplitude of the AE-signals for three different treatment levels are shown (the 10 % SST distribution is very similar to the 50 % SST distribution and is not shown). The number of AE-signals is lowest for the intermediate treatment level. In this graph, two distributions can be distinguished: correlation with the results obtained by microscopy showed that the AE-signals with a high PA are caused by unstable matrix cracking. Based on the characteristics of these signals (high PA, high ED, high RDC) a filter was chosen. This filter can be applied on materials with lower surface treatments. It results in a 1-1 correlation between the AE signals and the number of cracks spanning the entire specimen width (figure 3). It is not possible to use this filter on the AE-signals of the 100 % SST material, due to overlap with the AE-signals of another damage mode, as shown in figure 5c. Although all specimens are tested at the same maximum stress, and with the same stress amplitude, the 100 % SST material shows a high amount of signals with intermediate peak amplitude, event duration and number of ringdown counts. These signals are most probably created by fibre failure. As is mentioned in [4], a decrease in individual fibre strength is observed with increased fibre surface treatment. This effect is strengthened by the fact that almost no debonding is created at fibre fracture, resulting in increased stress concentrations [10]. The creation of fibre fracture will strongly decrease the lifetime of the composite. This was observed by stiffness degradation measurements. A strong decrease in longitudinal stiffness was found for the 100 % SST specimens. Therefore, it can be concluded the fatigue behaviour reaches an optimum at intermediate treatment levels, although the damage observed during the test, decreases with increased surface treatment level.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Fatigue tests were performed on specimens with differently surface treated fibres. Two different maximum stress levels were chosen: the first test series was based on the damage threshold during monotonic tensile loading. The second series all had the same maximum stress level. The following conclusions can be stated:

- The overall crack density decreases greatly with increased fibre surface treatment. 90° cracks, angle cracks and short 90° cracks decrease in density as the fibre-matrix quality is improved.
- The critical damage state, obtained by fatigue loading is different from the CDS of monotonic tensile loading: angle cracks and delaminations are created, resulting in a lower transverse crack density in the 90° ply.
- The relaxation of the shear stresses, created by load reintroduction into the 90° layer is done by delaminations and angle cracks. In the untreated material, no delaminations are present. As the surface treatment level increases, more delaminations and less angle cracks are formed, showing that the toughness of the 90° layer increases, compared to the matrix rich 0-90 interface layer.

- It is dangerous to draw conclusions concerning delaminations, based on light microscopy. Ultrasonic c-scanning is necessary to monitor the delamination density.
- From radiography measurements, it was shown that cracks, spanning the entire specimen thickness, immediately grow over the entire specimen width in an unstable way.
- From the AE-results, direct one-to-one correlation between high PA, high RDC and high ED events, and these unstable cracks could be found.
- The lowest AE-activity was found for the 50 % SST material. An increase of the activity was found in the 100 % SST material, most likely caused by fibre fracture. This was confirmed by stiffness degradation measurements during fatigue.

It can be concluded that, although the damage density in off-axis plies decreases continuously with increased surface treatment intensity, the best fatigue behaviour is found for intermediate (50 % SST) treatment levels.

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